

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF FISCAL POLICY IN ECONOMIC REGULATION

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the current state of the economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan and its fiscal policy. Alongside comparative analysis, the study utilizes a historical research methodology and conducts investigations. Additionally, specific analyses related to Azerbaijan in the Economic Freedom Index are included.

Keywords: economic regulation, growth, rule of law, fiscal policy, development.

Introduction

Under the conditions of a market economy, the primary task facing the Republic of Azerbaijan is to establish a truly democratic legal state based on diverse and equal rights for ownership and entrepreneurship, aligned with the progressive trends in the development of global states. Ensuring this balance in a globalized world is indeed a highly complex economic challenge.

In the modern economic environment, the goal is to create an efficient economy in the country by advancing production and its structure, based on high technology and techniques, in a manner that can meet the social and cultural needs of the population while improving the material interests of the citizens. Naturally, the role of the state in ensuring the normal functioning of the economic system is invaluable. The interaction between the state and the economy is one of the fundamental issues. Based on global experience, the state's influence on the economy is implemented in three main directions:

- Implementing an intervention policy corresponding to the adverse effects on the economy;
- Attempting to subordinate the economy to state control;
- Hindering economic development, thus causing deformations.

Considering the above points, it can be stated that state intervention in the economy can lead to either negative or positive trends in the economic development of any country. In the modern context, states predominantly favor the third approach.

It is more appropriate to determine the role of the state in a market economy by distinguishing three possible types of state activities. These functions primarily include increasing efficiency, ensuring equity, and stimulating macroeconomic stability and growth. Increasing efficiency refers to addressing negative manifestations arising from the natural development of the market economy, such as environmental pollution, monopolization, and similar issues. As Adam Smith stated, the advantages of the market mechanism are realized only when perfect competition is established. The existence of such a condition ensures that all goods and services are exchanged in the market at their true value,

preventing any buyer or seller from influencing market prices or the market as a whole.

Since monopoly—a process contrary to competition—has a profoundly negative impact on economic efficiency, combating it holds significant importance in modern state economic policy. The antitrust legislation first adopted in the United States was later implemented in unique forms across various countries. In the Republic of Azerbaijan, there is antitrust legislation as well as laws on competition, and to ensure the implementation of these laws, a special institution—the State Antimonopoly Policy and Support for Entrepreneurship Committee—operates. The main duty of this state body is to strengthen perfect competition and ensure the operation of the “invisible hand” in the economy. Such a mechanism, in turn, ensures the efficient use of resources and brings the economy closer to its production possibilities frontier. By ensuring that all economic sectors operate within the framework of perfect competition, the state creates conditions for markets to produce all the goods needed by society using the highest technologies and minimal resources.

However, fulfilling this task is complicated by the fact that the main characteristics of the market economy do not align with the criteria of perfect competition. The primary factors causing this mismatch include imperfect competition (e.g., monopolies), externalities (e.g., environmental pollution), and the need to ensure public welfare (e.g., national defense), all of which lead to the wastage of society's material wealth in various ways. In such a situation, only the power of the state can ensure the simultaneous and optimal resolution of all problems.

It should be noted that the foremost factor reducing market efficiency is imperfect competition or monopoly. While in a perfect competition environment no firm can significantly influence market prices, monopolistic conditions dictate the opposite. For example, if a telephone company or a labor union can influence telephone service or labor markets, respectively, it indicates the existence of a monopoly, regardless of whether it is accompanied by positive or negative outcomes. In cases where monopolization is inevitable and cannot be eliminated, the state strives to neutralize its

negative effects through direct intervention. Throughout the 20th century, most states pursued strict intervention policies to mitigate the consequences of imperfect competition. This primarily manifested in the regulation of prices and control over the income of monopolies.

Another issue that attracts significant attention from the state in a market economy is externalities. As technology and innovation advance, the scale of negative externalities the state has to address expands. Due to overall development, the volume of harmful products such as energy, chemicals, and other hazardous materials continuously increases, which makes combating these problems more challenging, including addressing the growing threat of environmental pollution. Solving such global problems requires not just the efforts of individual states but the combined efforts of all countries worldwide.

From this perspective, state regulation focuses significantly on addressing the negative externalities of production, such as water and air pollution, destructive use of natural resources, toxic waste, dangerous drugs, radioactive materials, and so on. All similar state efforts, from implementing safety measures in automobiles to regulating nuclear testing, ultimately serve one purpose: to enhance the general welfare of society, including economic well-being.

To fulfill its important responsibilities, the state must possess substantial financial resources. Taxes serve as the primary source of such resources. By adjusting tax rates for different incomes, offering tax incentives, and lowering the minimum levels of taxation, the state influences the economic cycle and seeks to ensure high rates of growth. One of the main tendencies of a market economy is the existence of a mechanism for distributing income based on the principles of social justice and equity. Earlier, the irreplaceable role of the state in efficiently utilizing the material and intellectual resources of society and ensuring the economy operates at its maximum production capacity was explained. However, even when such a condition is fully established, the state alone can ensure that the market economy operates on the basis of social equality.

The issue lies in the fact that numerous factors influence income—natural talent, education, inheritance, luck, as well as distortions in governance, such as corruption and organized crime—which contribute to income inequality. It should be noted that transfer payments provided by the state to the elderly, disabled, unemployed, and other disadvantaged individuals are one of the key factors in ensuring a fair distribution of income. Another method includes state subsidies to low-income groups, as well as grants in the areas of food, housing, and healthcare. Although such subsidies are relatively small compared to total income, they are accompanied by noticeable changes in the social and material security spheres.

Despite the extensive scope of the state's intervention in the economy, the free play of forces continues to give rise to chronic issues. Problems such as inflation, unemployment, and production crises, which accompany market economies, have only lost their severity in recent decades under the influence of comprehensive state economic policies.

A Theoretical Perspective on Fiscal Policy in the Creation of the Public Sector

As society developed, the role and functions of finance, taxation, and the budget in societal life changed. The comprehensive theoretical substantiation of finance, taxation, and the budget is a relatively recent phenomenon. Before the 17th century, all concepts about finance, taxation, and the budget were random and unsystematic, making it impossible to regard them as serious theoretical works. Over time, the transformation of temporary and extraordinary taxes into regular and general payments led to their rejection by the population. Such a situation required financial science to theoretically justify taxation.

The main theories of fiscal policy emerged from the 17th century onward as reviews of important economic principles. In economic literature, these are referred to as “general fiscal policy theories.” The main directions of these theories were shaped under the influence of societal economic development. Generally, fiscal policy theories refer to a system of knowledge about the essence and nature of finance, taxation, and the budget, as well as their place, role, and significance in society. In other words, fiscal policy theories reflect various models for organizing the state's financial, taxation, and budget systems.

In a broader sense, fiscal policy theories encompass both general scientific and theoretical research (general theories of finance, taxation, and budgets) and specific issues of taxation (specialized tax theories). Theories addressing the ratio among different types of taxes, the number of taxes, tax rates, and so on are called specialized tax theories. The theory of a “Unified Fiscal Policy” can be cited as an example of these specialized fiscal policy theories.

Thus, while general fiscal policy theories determine the overall purpose of taxation, finance, and the budget, specialized fiscal policy theories scientifically explain which types of taxes should be applied and their structure.

General Fiscal Policy Theories

One of the earliest general fiscal policy theories is the exchange theory. This theory is based on the reciprocal nature of taxation. The essence of the theory lies in the idea that taxpayers receive protection from external attacks and are provided with stable public conditions in exchange for the taxes they pay. This theory is only valid for the Middle Ages when military and legal protection was directly provided in exchange for taxes and fees. In such conditions, the exchange theory formally reflected the existing relationships.

During the Enlightenment, a variation of the exchange theory, known as the atomist theory, emerged. Its proponents included French Enlightenment thinkers like Sebastien Turgot, who developed the public exchange theory, and Charles Montesquieu, who proposed the social contract theory. According to this theory, taxation is the result of a contract between the state and its citizens. Taxpayers, in exchange for protection, public order, and other such services, pay taxes to the state. Just as no one can refuse the services provided by the state, no one can opt out of paying taxes. Such a contract is beneficial for citizens, as even the weakest

state can protect its citizens better and more cost-effectively than individuals can protect themselves independently. This perspective was supported by the English philosopher Thomas Hobbes and French thinkers like Butler and Honore Mirabeau.

In the first half of the 20th century, Swiss economist Jean Charles Léonard de Sismondi, in his work "New Principles of Political Economy," argued that taxes should be seen as the price paid by citizens for the services they receive from the state. The modern version of Sismondi's exchange tax theory forms the basis of contemporary exchange theories. During the same period, another theory emerged that viewed taxes as insurance premiums. Proponents of this theory included French statesman Adolphe Thiers and English economist John Ramsay McCulloch. According to them, taxes are insurance premiums paid by citizens to the state in case of risks like war, fire, or theft. However, unlike real insurance, taxes are not paid to receive compensation when risks occur but to finance the government's expenses for national defense and public order.

The insurance idea, which underpins this theory, can only be valid if the state undertakes the obligation to pay compensation to citizens in case of risk. For example, in Russia, under the "On Property in Russia" law of December 24, 1990, damages caused to property owners by criminal acts could be compensated by the state based on a court decision. However, this obligation was not directly linked to taxation and was effectively discontinued after Russia introduced a new tax system in 1992.

Thus, while the state's obligation to compensate for damages was established in Russian legislation, it was related more to political objectives than to taxation.

Classical Tax Theory

This theory was developed at a high scientific level and is associated with the names of English economists Adam Smith, David Ricardo, and their followers. Proponents of this theory viewed taxes as a type of state revenue that should cover government expenditures. Consequently, other roles of taxes, such as economic regulation, insurance payments, or service fees, were not considered.

This position was developed by Adam Smith and was based on the theory of market economy. In a market economy, meeting individual needs is ensured by granting economic and operational freedom to individuals. Adam Smith opposed the centralized management of the economy. He argued that the market economy has its own laws and that all processes occurring in the economy are subject to these laws. In his work "The Wealth of Nations," Adam Smith thoroughly analyzed the laws of the market economy and demonstrated that free competition, which is one of the main attributes of the market, leads prices to increasingly align with production costs. This, in turn, optimizes the allocation of resources within sectors.

Smith believed that the state should ensure the development of the market economy by protecting property rights. To perform these functions, the state requires appropriate resources. In a market economy, the share of direct state revenues (from state-owned properties) significantly decreases. As a result, tax revenues

become the primary source for covering state expenditures. Regarding other expenses, such as the construction and maintenance of roads or the operation of judicial institutions, Smith argued that they should be financed by fees paid by interested individuals. He also believed that taxes are non-compensatory by nature, and thus fees and charges cannot be considered taxes.

Polish economist Marie Esprit Léon Walras, a representative of classical theory, argued that the sole purpose of taxes is to finance state expenditures. The concept that taxes serve as a means to fill the state treasury is linked to the "night-watchman state" concept. However, the development of economic relations led to the transformation and softening of this theory.

Proponents of neoclassical tax theory, while not denying the impact of taxes on the economy, argued that taxation must be carefully considered to avoid disrupting economic processes. It is evident that classical theory does not hold up entirely, as it is practically impossible to channel one-quarter of the gross national product into the budget without causing serious economic consequences. Tax collection limits citizens' purchasing power, reduces entrepreneurs' investment opportunities, and indirect taxes raise product prices, negatively affecting consumption. All of this demonstrates that taxation significantly influences many economic processes in society.

Keynesian Tax Theory

One of the most important economic theories in the field of taxation is Keynesian theory. This theory was developed by English economist John Maynard Keynes. The main idea of this theory is that taxes are a key tool for regulating the economy and that it is impossible to develop the economy without them. According to Keynes' ideas, expressed in his book "The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money," economic growth depends on monetary savings under conditions of full employment. However, achieving full employment is practically impossible. In such circumstances, large savings become a passive source of income and, since they are not invested in production, they hinder economic growth. To eliminate these negative effects, savings must be collected into the budget through taxation.

Monetarist Tax Theory

The monetarist tax theory, proposed by Chicago University professor Milton Friedman in the 1950s, is based on the quantity theory of money. According to Friedman, the economy can be regulated through monetary circulation, which depends on the quantity of money and interest rates. Unlike Keynesian economic theory, Friedman did not consider taxes the main tool for economic regulation. In his view, taxes, along with other economic mechanisms, influence monetary circulation. Through taxes, excess money is withdrawn from the population.

According to both monetarist and Keynesian theories, taxes eliminate factors that negatively affect economic development.

Supply-Side Tax Theory

The supply-side tax theory, which places relatively more importance on taxation as a factor in economic development and regulation, was formed in the mid-1980s by American economists M. Burns, G.

Stein, and A. Laffer. This theory is based on the premise that high tax rates negatively affect entrepreneurship and investment activity, which ultimately leads to a decrease in tax payments. Proponents of this theory advocate for lowering tax rates and providing significant incentives to enterprises. They argue that reducing tax rates leads to rapid economic growth.

Specialized Fiscal Policy Theories

Among specialized fiscal policy theories, one of the earliest is the theory of the ratio between direct and indirect taxes. In the early stages of European civilization's development, the adoption of direct and indirect taxes depended on the political development of society. In medieval European cities, tax systems were primarily based on direct taxes. It was believed that indirect taxes, by increasing prices, negatively affected the population's situation and were more challenging to pay. Later, as the aristocracy gained strength to suppress public resistance, indirect taxes began to be implemented more widely. Indirect taxes were especially applied to essential goods, such as salt. Thus, during the Middle Ages, indirect taxes were viewed negatively.

By the late Middle Ages, a second perspective emerged, justifying the necessity of indirect taxes. It was argued that indirect taxes enabled the implementation of equitable taxation. Nobles, who used various exemptions, avoided paying direct taxes. Proponents of indirect taxes sought to compel privileged classes to pay taxes by implementing indirect taxation. They viewed indirect taxes as a means of creating equality in taxation. Adam Smith and David Ricardo, emphasizing the principle of voluntariness, also supported indirect taxation. This principle suggested that direct taxes were heavier than indirect ones, as individuals could avoid indirect taxes by not purchasing taxed goods.

By the late 19th century, economists debating the necessity of direct and indirect taxes concluded that it was essential to balance these two types of taxation. They argued that direct taxes were necessary to ensure equality in taxation, while indirect taxes were needed for efficient collection.

The Theory of the Single Tax

Another specialized tax theory is the single tax theory. It is worth noting that this theory addresses not only taxation but also broader social and political issues. The idea of a single tax gained popularity at various times. For instance, in 18th-century England, there was a political party whose slogan was "A Single Tax on Land." Advocates of the single tax claimed that its implementation would eliminate poverty and lead to increased production across all industrial sectors.

A single tax is a unique tax applied to a specific taxation object. Different theorists have proposed various objects for single taxation, such as land, expenses, income, capital, and others. One of the earliest forms of the single tax is the tax on land rent. The idea of applying this tax was put forward by the physiocrats. They considered agriculture the primary production sector and argued that industrial activities did not contribute any net income. All wealth, they claimed, was concentrated in the land and derived from it. Therefore, they proposed a single tax on land rent as the sole source of revenue. Accordingly, this tax would be paid exclu-

sively by landowners. To justify this single tax, they relied on the idea of the "universality of land." They argued that land is a divine gift and belongs to everyone. However, in reality, land is owned by specific individuals who hold the sole source of wealth and, therefore, should pay the single tax.

In the 19th century, Henry George advanced the idea of the "single land tax," viewing it as a means of ensuring general prosperity and creating social harmony. It should be noted, however, that the single tax theory cannot be considered a progressive theory. Despite some advantages, such as simplicity in calculation and payment, the theory is utopian and practically impossible to implement. Nonetheless, the application of a single tax in conjunction with other taxation systems could yield positive results. The idea of a single tax is also reflected in Russia's tax system. According to the federal law "On the Simplification of Accounting and Reporting for Taxation" (effective December 24, 1995), some small enterprises and entrepreneurs could pay a single tax calculated based on the results of their economic activities during the reporting period, instead of numerous federal, regional, and local taxes. The implementation of such a tax in Russia can be seen as a progressive step, as it simplifies taxation for small business entities.

Progressive and Proportional Taxation

The social and political nature of taxes has significantly influenced the theoretical aspects of taxation. This is particularly evident in the theories addressing the ratio between progressive and proportional taxes. Taxes, being a means of expropriating part of the property, reflect class and group interests as well as the balance of social forces. According to the theory of proportional taxation, taxes should be levied at a uniform rate, regardless of income level. This idea has always been supported by wealthier segments of the population, as it aligns with the principles of equality and social justice.

In contrast, progressive taxation implies that tax rates increase as income levels rise. Progressive tax rates were positively evaluated by socialist ideologues Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels, who argued in the Communist Manifesto that progressive taxation could play a role in abolishing private property and establishing socialism. Although the theory of progressive taxation emerged in the late 19th century, elements of this theory can be found in the works of Adam Smith, as well as French Enlightenment thinkers like Jean-Jacques Rousseau and Jean-Baptiste Say.

Proponents of progressive taxation argue that it reduces inequality and influences the redistribution of income and wealth.

Tax Shifting Theories

One of the fundamental issues in taxation, reflected in tax theories, is the concept of "tax shifting." Although this issue has significant practical importance, it has been underexplored. The essence of tax shifting theories lies in the idea that the distribution of tax burdens is possible only during the process of exchange.

Methods of Fiscal Policy

In a globalizing world, the independent actions of entrepreneurs do not always lead to successful economic outcomes. For this reason, it is advisable for the state to intervene in entrepreneurial activities through certain economic instruments. Currently, it is appropriate to classify the market regulation methods in the Republic of Azerbaijan as follows:

1. State methods;
2. Non-state methods.

Of course, each method has its specific characteristics. Through state methods, the government has the ability to influence the entire political and economic life of the country, which inevitably affects the economic life of the entire population. Experience shows that the state, in one way or another, identifies the opportunities to meet the needs of every citizen. The methods by which a state regulates its economy are among the most intriguing economic issues.

Since gaining independence, the Republic of Azerbaijan has been implementing its economic policies in the direction of private property ownership and the functioning of market mechanisms.

As a continuation of the political and economic reforms initiated by the national leader Heydar Aliyev, the political and economic role of our country in the modern economic environment has significantly changed, transforming Azerbaijan into a regional power. The successful reforms have been diligently continued, expanded, and brought to new heights by the successor of Azerbaijan's political-economic course, President Ilham Aliyev, resulting in the creation of a new model for state regulation of the economy through market mechanisms.

In leading countries of the world, state regulation is primarily implemented through laws, the main economic tool of taxation, regulating monetary circulation, and ensuring production infrastructure (such as industrial parks).

Based on the above, reforms should be carried out in a way that prevents discrimination among different social groups in the country. In this regard, special attention should be paid to the social functions fulfilled by economic reforms implemented by the state.

The state continually oversees the implementation of activities in areas of economic activity that are not attractive for entrepreneurship. These areas include sectors where the application of special investments is not profitable. According to global practice, these are primarily material and non-material production sectors that require long-term investments. Such areas generally include:

- Education;
- Healthcare;
- Other material production sectors.

In the modern economic environment, significant efforts are being made to direct the income generated from Azerbaijan's oil sector toward the development of a new, diversified economy.

According to economic theory, world-renowned economists P. Samuelson and V. Nordhaus believe that in a modern mixed economy, the primary economic functions of the state include the following:

1. Establishing the legal foundations for the economic activities of legal and natural persons;
2. Implementing a macroeconomic stabilization policy;
3. Facilitating the allocation of resources to improve economic efficiency;
4. Developing programs that impact income distribution.

Currently, it can be said with full confidence that the preparation of legislative acts and regulations on macroeconomic regulation in the Republic of Azerbaijan is being carried out at the necessary level under the leadership of the country's administration.

It can also be confidently stated that since the late 20th century, statehood in the Republic of Azerbaijan has been significantly strengthened and has been utilized to safeguard common interests and the overall economic system.

Another important economic strategy implemented in our country is ensuring macroeconomic stability. The priority issue in achieving macroeconomic stability is mitigating industrial cycles in the country. This, in turn, involves specific economic measures aimed at addressing unemployment and inflation in our republic.

For this purpose, the following methods are utilized:

1. Regulating the economy through taxation;
2. Regulating the money supply in the country's balance of payments.

The methods listed above individually serve to implement the state's specific economic policies. Among them, regulating the economy through fiscal and budgetary tools is the essence of the state's fiscal policy, while regulating the money supply in the balance of payments constitutes the main focus of monetary methods.

Conclusion

The monetary and financial-credit system plays a crucial role in ensuring economic stability. Intervention in the monetary and financial-credit system refers to the implementation of flexible tax policies, proper credit strategies, and the regulation of monetary circulation in the country. A positive effect of the state's influence on the economy is preventing dangerous stratification among producers and maintaining balance. The following methods, tested and proven effective in global practice, can be highlighted for ensuring competitiveness:

1. Progressive income taxation;
2. Setting low prices for goods that ensure a minimum standard of living;
3. Training and retraining of specialists, and the creation of new jobs.

When the state intervenes in the economy, the following economic elements must be consistently monitored:

- Ensuring minimum wages and pension guarantees;
- Indexing incomes as prices change;
- Providing benefits to temporarily unemployed individuals, and others.

One of the main objectives of the state's monetary policy is the issuance of additional monetary resources

into circulation to artificially enhance consumers' purchasing power. The essence of this goal is as follows:

Another fundamental issue of monetary policy is preventing deep inflation and maintaining it at a specific level.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that one of the primary tasks of the state's influence on the economy is to help distribute resources in a socially just manner. The implementation of such an economic-political approach is one of the key aspects of ensuring macroeconomic stability.

Non-state methods are also used in regulating the country's economy. In this case, the main focus is placed on the following economic elements:

- Sales markets;
- Various associations that agree on prices;
- Banks;
- Stock exchanges;
- Fairs;
- Wholesale trade centers;
- Currency auctions;
- Information systems, and others.

As the economy operates as an inseparable part of the state in a globalizing world, the methods of its reg-

ulation must be continuously improved, advanced practices must be widely utilized, and measures must be taken based on specific circumstances.

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